

SYNTHESIS AND REACTIONS OF α -BROMO- α -ISONITROSO-ACETOPHENONE AND α -BROMO- α -ISONITROSO-(*p*-METHOXY, *p*-CHLORO, AND *p*-BROMO)-ACETOPHENONES

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α -Bromo- α -isonitroso-acetophenones have been synthesised and characterised. These do not contain oxidising bromine atoms unlike bromo-oxymethylene compounds.

Synthesis and reactions of bromonitroso ketones (I) and bromoisnitroso ketones (II) have not been studied. These compounds can be compared well with the corresponding bromoformyl ketones (III) and (IV). A study of the properties of these compounds and comparison with those of (III) and (IV) are expected to furnish a relative idea of the reactivity of halogen in the two pentad systems (V) and (VI).

In the present investigation, synthesis of α -bromo- α -isonitroso- (VII: X = H), *p*-methoxy- (VII: X = OMe), *p*-chloro- (VII: X = Cl) and *p*-bromo-acetophenones (VII: X = Br) have been successfully carried out and their properties studied. These bromo compounds have been obtained by bromination of *isonitroso*-acetophenones either in the free form or in the form of their metallic salts.

In attempts to prepare these compounds by the nitrosation of phenacyl bromides in the presence of hydrogen chloride, the authors obtained the corresponding α -chloro- α -isonitroso compounds (cf. Levin and Hartung, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1942, 7, 408). The α -bromo compounds, however, were obtained by

controlling the quantity of hydrogen chloride and reducing the time of contact to 2½ hours. Bromination of sodium and copper salts gave benzoic acids (VII: CO-CHBr-NO is COOH) along with bromo compounds and in some cases the acid was the main product. Attempts to prepare these compounds by the action of *N*-bromosuccinimide on free isonitrosoacetophenones gave benzoic acids.

The four bromoisnitroso ketones are solid crystalline compounds, insoluble in water, sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride and soluble in ether, benzene and petroleum ether. Their melting points are higher as compared to those of the corresponding bromo-oxymethylene-acetophenones (cf. Garg and Bokadia this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 286). These do not develop any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution, but on standing for some time in contact with the reagent develop a violet colour. They reduce Fehling's solution and show a wine-red colour with pyridine.

Bromo-oxymethylene ketones (III and IV) liberate iodine on being warmed with acidified potassium iodide solution, generating the halogen-free parent oxymethylene ketones (inverse substitution) (Bokadia, *Agra. Univ. J. Res.*, 1953, 2, 9; Garg, Garg and Bokadia, *ibid.*, 1957, 6, 19; Bokadia and Deshapande, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 548; Garg and Bokadia, *loc. cit.*). But in the case of α -bromo- α -isonitrosoacetophenones, studied herein, halogen has been found to be very stable and devoid of oxidising properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of α -Bromo- α -isonitrosoacetophenone

Method I: Bromination of Sodium Salt of isoNitrosoacetophenone.—Sodium ethylate (6.8 g.) was taken in a R.B. flask fitted with a calcium chloride guard tube. It was covered with dry ether and cooled well in ice. An equimolecular mixture of acetophenone (12 c.c.) and pure amyl nitrite (13 c.c.) was added to it gradually in several instalments with constant shaking. The contents were kept at 0°. The sodium salt was filtered, washed with dry ether, dried, suspended in dry CCl₄ and cooled well. To this a solution of bromine (2 atoms), dissolved in the same solvent, was added slowly. The precipitated sodium bromide was filtered off and from the filtrate the solvent was removed. The residual thick syrupy liquid immediately solidified. The product was found to be a mixture of benzoic acid and α -bromo- α -isonitrosoacetophenone. From this mixture benzoic acid was removed by NaHCO₃. The bromo compound was crystallised in a very poor yield from a mixture of CCl₄ and benzene, m.p. 137°.

Method II: Bromination of Copper Complex.—To an alcoholic solution of isonitrosoacetophenone (15 g.) a saturated solution of copper acetate was added gradually. The precipitated copper salt was purified by repeated washing with petroleum ether, m.p. 210° (decomp.). (Found: Cu, 20.1. C₁₄H₁₃O₄N₂Cu requires Cu, 17.7%). The copper complex (22 g.) was suspended in dry ether, cooled and a solution of bromine (19.5 g.) was added to it. The contents were kept overnight and then washed with water twice and dried. On evaporation it gave a mixture of benzoic

acid and the bromo compound from which the latter on crystallisation melted at 137° , yield 6 g. (Found: C, 42.7; H, 2.9; N, 7.1; Br, 36.9. $C_8H_6O_2NBr$ requires C, 42.15; H, 2.63; N, 6.14; Br, 35.1%).

Method III: Bromination in Pyridine.—Free isonitrosoacetophenone (3 g.) was taken in a three-necked flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer. Sodium-dried pyridine (2 g.), benzene (25 c.c.) and ether (10 c.c.) were added to it. The mixture was well cooled and bromine (3.2 g.) was added to it gradually with constant shaking. After the addition of bromine the reactants were allowed to stand for 3 hours to complete the reaction. The product was washed with water, dried over fused calcium chloride and evaporated, yielding a gummy mass from which the bromo compound was obtained in a very poor yield by petroleum ether, m.p. 137° .

Method IV: Nitrosation of Phenacyl Bromide in presence of HCl .—A three-necked R.B. flask (500 c.c.) was fitted with a small dropping funnel, a mechanical stirrer, a reflux condenser, connected to an exit tube having a calcium chloride guard tube at the other end, and a hydrogen chloride delivery tube which extended to the bottom of the flask.

Phenacyl bromide (4.1 g.) and dry ether (50 c.c.) were taken in the reaction flask. The stirrer was started and after the solid had dissolved, a current of dry HCl gas was passed. To this mixture isopropyl nitrite (4.5 g.) was added in several instalments. After addition of the first instalment, the reaction mixture became orange-brown and after several minutes, light yellow. At this stage a next instalment was added. After completion of the addition it was left overnight. From the reaction mixture ether was removed and also the unchanged isopropyl nitrite and isopropyl alcohol (under reduced pressure). The residue on evaporation gave a solid mass which melted at 135° after crystallisation from CCl_4 and benzene mixture (2:1). It was found to contain chlorine. (Found: C, 50.42; H, 3.13; N, 6.65; Cl, 20.0. $C_8H_6O_2NCl$ requires C, 52.3; H, 3.2; N, 7.9; Cl, 19.3%).

In the next attempt the reaction mixture after the addition of the reactants was kept only for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours and then it was treated with 10 c.c. of water. The organic layer was dried over fused calcium chloride and evaporated. The solid product melted at 137° after crystallisation, yield 4 g.

Method V: Bromination with N-Bromosuccinimide.—Isonitrosoacetophenone (2.3 g.), dry CCl_4 (10 c.c.) and N-bromosuccinimide (2.7 g.) were taken in a 50 c.c. R.B. flask and gently refluxed for 1 hour. After the reaction the filtrate gave a solid on evaporation, which was found to be benzoic acid.

α -Bromo- α -isonitrosoacetophenone is a colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 137° . It is soluble in benzene and ether, insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in CCl_4 . It does not give any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution, but on standing it develops a violet colour. When warmed with acidified potassium iodide solution it does not liberate iodine. It reduces Fehling's solution and gives a wine-red colour with pyridine. It has got a strong irritating effect.

*Synthesis of α -Bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenone*

Method I: Bromination of Sodium Salt.—The sodium salt of *isonitroso-p*-methoxyacetophenone was brominated in the same manner as in the case of acetophenone. The solid product that was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 182° , was solely *p*-methoxybenzoic acid.

Method II: Bromination of Copper Complex.—Bromination of copper complex (m.p. 150° d. Found: Cu, 12.0. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6N_2Cu$ requires Cu, 15.1%) was effected in the same manner as in the case of acetophenone and gave a solid product which was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and CCl_4 (1:2), m.p. 139° . (Found: C, 42.1; H, 3.5; N, 5.5; Br, 30.9. $C_9H_8O_5NBr$ requires C, 41.8; H, 3.1; N, 5.42; Br, 31.0%).

Method III: Nitrosation of p-Methoxyphenacyl Bromide in presence of HCl.—Nitrosation of *p*-methoxyphenacyl bromide was done in the same manner as described in the case of acetophenone, but the product was α -chloro- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenone, melting at 142° , yield 2 g. (Found: C, 49.16; H, 3.85; N, 6.24; Cl, 16.1. $C_9H_8O_5NCl$ requires C, 49.1; H, 3.7; N, 6.5; Cl, 16.6%).

But by limiting the time of contact with HCl to 2 hours, α -bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenone was obtained which was crystallised from a mixture (2:1) of benzene and CCl_4 , m.p. 139° .

α -Bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenone is a colorless crystalline solid, soluble in benzene, ether and alcohol, insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in CCl_4 . It does not give any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution, but on standing it develops a violet colour. When warmed with acidified potassium iodide solution, it does not liberate iodine. It reduces Fehling's solution and gives a wine-red colour with pyridine.

*Synthesis of α -Bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-bromoacetophenone*

Method I: Bromination of sodium salt gave *p*-bromobenzoic acid, m.p. 251° .

Method II: Bromination of copper complex (m.p. 210° . Found: Cu, 12.7. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4N_2Br_2Cu$ requires Cu, 12.2%) gave α -bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-bromoacetophenone, m.p. 141° from the same solvent mixture as used previously. (Found: C, 31.27; H, 1.62; N, 4.56; Br, 51.59. $C_8H_5O_2NBr_2$ requires C, 33.52; H, 1.9; N, 4.3; Br, 52.5%).

Method III: Nitrosation of p-bromophenacyl bromide in the presence of hydrogen chloride gave α -bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-bromoacetophenone; by limiting the time of contact with HCl, a solid product was obtained, m.p. 141° , from the same solvent mixture, yield 5 g.

α -Bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-bromoacetophenone is a colorless crystalline solid, soluble in benzene and alcohol, insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in CCl_4 and ether. It does not give any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution, but on standing develops a violet colour. It does not liberate iodine on being warmed with acidified KI solution. It reduces Fehling's solution and gives a wine-red colour with pyridine.

*Synthesis of α -Bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-chloroacetophenone*

Method I: Bromination of sodium salt gave *p*-chlorobenzoic acid, m.p. 235° .

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Method II: Bromination of copper complex (m.p. 130° d. Found: Cu, 14.2. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2Cl_2Cu$ requires Cu, 14.8%) gave a solid product which was crystallised from CCl_4 , m.p. 140° . (Found: C, 36.57; H, 1.9; N, 5.3; Br + Cl, 44.9. $C_8H_5O_2NClBr$ requires C, 36.60; H, 1.95; N, 5.3; Br + Cl, 44%).

Method III: Nitrosation of p-chlorophenacyl bromide in presence of HCl gas gave α -chloro- α -isonitroso-*p*-chloroacetophenone, m.p. 124° . (Found: C, 43.5; H, 2.52; N, 5.92; Cl, 32.1. Calc. for $C_8H_5O_2NCl_2$: C, 44.03; H, 2.2; N, 6.4; Cl, 32.5%).

Nitrosation of *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide by limiting the time of contact with hydrogen chloride gave a solid which melted at 140° after crystallisation, yield 4 g.

α -Bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-chloroacetophenone is a colorless crystalline solid, soluble in benzene, ether and alcohol, insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in CCl_4 . It does not give any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution, but on standing develops a violet colour. It does not liberate iodine on being warmed with acidified potassium iodide solution. It reduces Fehling's solution and gives a wine-red colour with pyridine. It has got a strong irritating effect.

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